

Relations on Interval Valued Neutrosophic Soft Sets

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Abstract. Anjan Mukherjee [43] introduced the concept of interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy soft relation. In this paper we will extend this concept to the case of interval valued neutrosophic soft relation(IVNSS relation for short) which can be discussed as a generalization of soft relations, fuzzy soft relation, intuitionistic fuzzy soft relation, interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy soft relations and neutrosophic soft relations [44]. Basic operations are presented and the various properties like reflexivity, symmetry, transitivity of IVNSS relations are also studied.

Keywords: Neutrosophic soft sets, Interval valued neutrosophic soft sets, Interval valued neutrosophic soft relation.

I.Introduction

In 1999, Florentin Smarandache introduced the theory of neutrosophic set (NS) [1], which is the generalization of the classical sets, conventional fuzzy set [2], intuitionistic fuzzy set [3] and interval valued fuzzy set [4]. This concept has been successfully applied to many fields such as Databases [5,6], Medical diagnosis problem [7], Decision making problem [8], Topology [9], control theory [10] etc. The concept of neutrosophic set handle indeterminate data whereas fuzzy set theory, and intuitionistic fuzzy set theory failed when the relation are indeterminate.

Presently work on the neutrosophic set theory is progressing rapidly. Bhowmik and M.Pal [11,12] defined "intuitionistic neutrosophic set". Later on A.A.Salam, S.A.Alblowi [13] introduced another concept called "Generalized neutrosophic set". Wang et al [14] proposed another extension of neutrosophic set which is "single valued neutrosophic". Also Wang et al [15] introduced the notion of interval valued neutrosophic set which is an instance of neutrosophic set. It is characterized by an interval membership degree, interval indeterminacy degree and interval non-membership degree. K.Geogiev [16] Ye [17, 18], P. Majumdar and S.K. Samant [19]. S.Broumi and F. Smarandache [20,21,22] L.Peid [23], and so on

In 1999 a Russian researcher, Molodotsov proposed a new mathematical tool called "Soft set theory" [24], for dealing with uncertainty and how soft set theory is free from the parameterization inadequacy syndrome of fuzzy set theory, rough set theory, probability theory.

Although there many authors [25,26,27,28,29,32,33] have contributed a lot towards fuzzification which leads to a series of mathematical models such as Fuzzy soft set generalized fuzzy soft set, possibility fuzzy soft set, fuzzy parameterized soft set and so on, intuitionistic fuzzy soft set which is based on a combination of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets and soft set models. Later a lot of extensions of intuitionistic fuzzy soft [34] are appeared such as Generalized intuitionistic fuzzy soft set [35], Possibility Intuitionistic Fuzzy Soft Set [36] and so on . Few studies are focused on neutrosophication of soft set theory. In [37] P.K.Maji, first proposed a new mathematical model called “Neutrosophic Soft Set” and investigate some properties regarding neutrosophic soft union, neutrosophic soft intersection ,complement of a neutrosophic soft set ,De Morgan law etc. Furthermore , in 2013, S.Broumi and F. Smarandache [38] combined the intuitionistic neutrosophic and soft set which lead to a new mathematical model called” intuitionistic neutrosophic soft set”. They studied the notions of intuitionistic neutrosophic soft set union, intuitionistic neutrosophic soft set intersection, complement of intuitionistic neutrosophic soft set and several other properties of intuitionistic neutrosophic soft set along with examples and proofs of certain results. Also ,in [39] S.Broumi presented the concept of “Generalized neutrosophic soft set” by combining the Generalized Neutrosophic Sets [40] and Soft set Models ,studied some properties on it, and presented an application of Generalized Neutrosophic Soft Set [39] in decision making problem. S.Broumi and F.smarandache [41] introduced the necessity and possibility operators on intuitionistic neutrosophic and investigated some properties.

Recently, Irfan Deli [42] introduced the concept of interval valued neutrosophic soft set [42] as a combination of interval neutrosophic set and soft set. This concept generalizes the concept of the soft set [24], fuzzy soft set[26], intuitionistic fuzzy soft set [34],interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy soft set[43] ,the concept of neutrosophic soft set[37] and intuitionistic neutrosophic soft set [38].

This paper is an attempt to extend the concept of interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy soft relation (IVIFSS-relations) introduced by A.Mukherjee et al [45]to IVNSS relation .

The organization of this paper is as follow : In section 2, we briefly present some basic definitions and preliminary results are given which will be used in the rest of the paper. In section 3, relation interval neutrosophic soft relation is presented. In section 4 varouis type of interval valued neutrosophic soft relations. In section 5, we concludes the paper.

II.Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, let U be a universal set and E be the set of all possible parameters under consideration with respect to U , usually, parameters are attributes , characteristics, or properties of objects in U . We now recall some basic notions of neutrosophic set , interval neutrosophic set ,soft set , neutrosophic soft set and interval neutrosophic soft set.

For more details, the reader may refer to [5,6,8,9,12].

Definition 1 (see[3]).Neutrosophic set

Let U be an universe of discourse then the neutrosophic set A is an object having the form $A = \{ < x:$

$\mu_{A(x)}, \nu_{A(x)}, \omega_{A(x)} \in]0, 1[$, where the functions $\mu, \nu, \omega : U \rightarrow]0, 1[$ define respectively the degree of membership, the degree of indeterminacy, and the degree of non-membership of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition.

$$0 \leq \mu_{A(x)} + \nu_{A(x)} + \omega_{A(x)} \leq 3^+$$

From philosophical point of view, the neutrosophic set takes the value from real standard or non-standard subsets of $]0, 1[$. so instead of $]0, 1[$ we need to take the interval $[0, 1]$ for technical applications, because $]0, 1[$ will be difficult to apply in the real applications such as in scientific and engineering problems.

Definition 2 (see [3]). A neutrosophic set A is contained in another neutrosophic set B i.e. $A \subseteq B$ if $\forall x \in U, \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) \leq \nu_B(x), \omega_A(x) \geq \omega_B(x)$.

A complete account of the operations and application of neutrosophic set can be seen in [3] [10].

Definition 3 (see[7]). Interval neutrosophic set

Let X be a space of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . An interval valued neutrosophic set (for short IVNS) A in X is characterized by truth-membership function $\mu_A(x)$, indeterminacy-membership function $\nu_A(x)$ and falsity-membership function $\omega_A(x)$. For each point x in X , we have that $\mu_A(x), \nu_A(x), \omega_A(x) \in [0, 1]$.

For two IVNS, $A_{IVNS} = \{ \langle x, [\mu_A^L(x), \mu_A^U(x)], [\nu_A^L(x), \nu_A^U(x)], [\omega_A^L(x), \omega_A^U(x)] \rangle \mid x \in X \}$

And $B_{IVNS} = \{ \langle x, [\mu_B^L(x), \mu_B^U(x)], [\nu_B^L(x), \nu_B^U(x)], [\omega_B^L(x), \omega_B^U(x)] \rangle \mid x \in X \}$ the two relations are defined as follows:

(1) $A_{IVNS} \subseteq B_{IVNS}$ if and only if $\mu_A^L(x) \leq \mu_B^L(x), \mu_A^U(x) \leq \mu_B^U(x), \nu_A^L(x) \geq \nu_B^L(x), \nu_A^U(x) \geq \nu_B^U(x), \omega_A^L(x) \geq \omega_B^L(x), \omega_A^U(x) \geq \omega_B^U(x)$,

(2) $A_{IVNS} = B_{IVNS}$ if and only if, $\mu_A(x) = \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) = \nu_B(x), \omega_A(x) = \omega_B(x)$ for any $x \in X$

As an illustration, let us consider the following example.

Example 1. Assume that the universe of discourse $U = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$, where x_1 characterizes the capability, x_2 characterizes the trustworthiness and x_3 indicates the prices of the objects. It may be further assumed that the values of x_1, x_2 and x_3 are in $[0, 1]$ and they are obtained from some questionnaires of some experts. The experts may impose their opinion in three components viz. the degree of goodness, the degree of indeterminacy and that of poorness to explain the characteristics of the objects. Suppose A is an interval neutrosophic set (INS) of U , such that,
 $A = \{ \langle x_1, [0.3 \ 0.4], [0.5 \ 0.6], [0.4 \ 0.5] \rangle, \langle x_2, [0.1 \ 0.2], [0.3 \ 0.4], [0.6 \ 0.7] \rangle, \langle x_3, [0.2 \ 0.4], [0.4 \ 0.5], [0.4 \ 0.6] \rangle \}$, where the degree of goodness of capability is 0.3, degree of indeterminacy of capability is 0.5 and degree of falsity of capability is 0.4 etc.

Definition 4 (see[4]). Soft set

Let U be an initial universe set and E be a set of parameters. Let $P(U)$ denotes the power set of U . Consider a nonempty set $A, A \subset E$. A pair (K, A) is called a soft set over U , where K is a mapping given by $K : A \rightarrow P(U)$.

As an illustration, let us consider the following example.

Example 2 . Suppose that U is the set of houses under consideration, say $U = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_5\}$. Let E be the set of some attributes of such houses, say $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_8\}$, where $e_1, e_2, \dots, e_8$ stand for the attributes “beautiful”, “costly”, “in the green surroundings”, “moderate”, respectively.

In this case, to define a soft set means to point out expensive houses, beautiful houses, and so on. For example, the soft set (K, A) that describes the “attractiveness of the houses” in the opinion of a buyer, say Thomas, may be defined like this:

$$A = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5\};$$

$$K(e_1) = \{h_2, h_3, h_5\}, K(e_2) = \{h_2, h_4\}, K(e_3) = \{h_1\}, K(e_4) = U, K(e_5) = \{h_3, h_5\}.$$

Definition 5 [] (interval neutrosophic soft set) .

Let U be an initial universe set and $A \subset E$ be a set of parameters. Let $IVNS(U)$ denotes the set of all interval neutrosophic subsets of U . The collection (K,A) is termed to be the soft interval neutrosophic set over U , where F is a mapping given by $K : A \rightarrow IVNS(U)$.

The interval neutrosophic soft set defined over an universe is denoted by INSS.

To illustrate let us consider the following example:

Let U be the set of houses under consideration and E is the set of parameters (or qualities). Each parameter is a interval neutrosophic word or sentence involving interval neutrosophic words. Consider $E = \{ beautiful, costly, in the green surroundings, moderate, expensive \}$. In this case, to define a interval neutrosophic soft set means to point out beautiful houses, costly houses, and so on. Suppose that, there are five houses in the universe U given by, $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4, h_5\}$ and the set of parameters $A = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$, where each e_i is a specific criterion for houses:

- e_1 stands for ‘beautiful’,
- e_2 stands for ‘costly’,
- e_3 stands for ‘in the green surroundings’,
- e_4 stands for ‘moderate’,

Suppose that,

$$K(\text{beautiful}) = \{ \langle h_1, [0.5, 0.6], [0.6, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_2, [0.4, 0.5], [0.7, 0.8], [0.2, 0.3] \rangle, \langle h_3, [0.6, 0.7], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.5] \rangle, \langle h_4, [0.7, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_5, [0.8, 0.4], [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle \}.$$

$$K(\text{costly}) = \{ \langle h_1, [0.5, 0.6], [0.6, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_2, [0.4, 0.5], [0.7, 0.8], [0.2, 0.3] \rangle, \langle h_3, [0.6, 0.7], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.5] \rangle, \langle h_4, [0.7, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_5, [0.8, 0.4], [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle \}.$$

$$K(\text{in the green surroundings}) = \{ \langle h_1, [0.5, 0.6], [0.6, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_2, [0.4, 0.5], [0.7, 0.8], [0.2, 0.3] \rangle, \langle h_3, [0.6, 0.7], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.5] \rangle, \langle h_4, [0.7, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_5, [0.8, 0.4], [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle \}.$$

$$K(\text{moderate}) = \{ \langle h_1, [0.5, 0.6], [0.6, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_2, [0.4, 0.5], [0.7, 0.8], [0.2, 0.3] \rangle, \langle h_3, [0.6, 0.7], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.5] \rangle, \langle h_4, [0.7, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.4] \rangle, \langle h_5, [0.8, 0.4], [0.2, 0.6], [0.3, 0.4] \rangle \}.$$

III. Relations on Interval Valued Neutrosophic Soft Sets

Definition 6.

Let U be an initial universe and (F,A) and (G,B) be two interval valued neutrosophic soft set . Then a relation between them is defined as a pair $(H, Ax B)$, where H is mapping given by $H: Ax B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$. This is called an interval valued neutrosophic soft sets relation (IVNSS-relation for short).the collection of relations on interval valued neutrosophic soft sets on $Ax B$ over U is denoted by $\sigma_U(Ax B)$

Remark 1: Let U be an initial universe and $(F_1, A_1), (F_2, A_2), \dots, (F_n, A_n)$, be n numbers of interval valued neutrosophic soft sets over U . Then a relation σ between them is defined as a pair $(H, A_1 \times A_2 \times \dots \times A_n)$, where H is mapping given by $H: A_1 \times A_2 \times \dots \times A_n \rightarrow \text{IVIFS}(U)$

Example 3. (i) Let us consider an interval valued neutrosophic soft set (F, A) which describes the 'attractiveness of the houses' under consideration. Let the universe set $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4, h_5\}$. and the set of parameter $A = \{\text{beautiful}(e_1), \text{in the green surroundings}(e_3)\}$.

Then the tabular representation of the interval valued neutrosophic soft set (F, A) is given below:

U	beautiful(e_1)	in the green surroundings (e_3)
h_1	$([0.5, 0.6], [0.3, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4])$	$([0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.8])$
h_2	$([0.2, 0.5], [0.4, 0.7], [0.5, 0.6])$	$([0.4, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4])$
h_3	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.7, 0.9], [0.1, 0.2])$	$([0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.3], [0.4, 0.5])$
h_4	$([0.1, 0.7], [0.2, 0.4], [0.6, 0.7])$	$([0.5, 0.6], [0.4, 0.5], [0.3, 0.4])$
h_5	$([0.4, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3], [0.5, 0.6])$

(ii) Now Let us consider an interval valued neutrosophic soft set (G, A) which describes the 'cost of the houses' under consideration. Let the universe set $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4, h_5\}$. and the set of parameter $A = \{\text{costly}(e_2), \text{moderate}(e_4)\}$.

Then the tabular representation of the interval valued neutrosophic soft set (G, b) is given below:

U	costly(e_2)	moderate (e_4)
h_1	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.7, 0.9], [0.1, 0.2])$	$([0.4, 0.6], [0.7, 0.8], [0.1, 0.4])$
h_2	$([0.6, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4], [0.1, 0.7])$	$([0.1, 0.5], [0.4, 0.7], [0.5, 0.6])$
h_3	$([0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.7], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.4])$
h_4	$([0.6, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.7, 0.9], [0.1, 0.2])$
h_5	$([0.2, 0.6], [0.2, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5])$	$([0.5, 0.6], [0.6, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4])$

Let us consider the two IVNSS-relations P and Q on the two given interval valued neutrosophic soft sets given below:

$P = (H, A \times B)$

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h_1	$([0.2, 0.4], [0.3, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2])$	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0.3, 0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.5], [0.3, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5])$	$([0.4, 0.5], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 1])$
h_2	$([0.1, 0.3], [0.4, 0.5], [1, 1])$	$([0.1, 0.2], [0, 0], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.5], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4], [0.4, 0.5])$
h_3	$([0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.4], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([0.2, 0.6], [0.1, 0.3], [1, 1])$	$([0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.3], [0.3, 0.6])$	$([0.2, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3], [0, 0.4])$
h_4	$([0.2, 0.4], [0.3, 0.5], [0, 1])$	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.4, 0.5], [0.1, 0.2])$	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.3, 0.4], [0.4, 0.5])$	$([0, 0.2], [0.4, 0.5], [0.6, 0.7])$

$Q = (J, A \times B)$

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H ₁	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.3,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.3, 0.6],[0.2, 1]]
h ₂	[[0.1,0.3],[0.4, 0.5],[1, 1]]	[[0.1, 0.2],[0, 0],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.4],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.3],[0.3,0.6]]	[[0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.4]]
h ₄	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 1]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.4,0.5]]	[[0, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5],[0.6,0.7]]

The tabular representations of P and Q are called relational matrices for P and Q respectively. From above we have , $\mu_{H(e_1,e_2)}(h_1) = [0.2 ,0.3]$, $\nu_{H(e_1,e_2)}(h_2) = [0.3 , 0.4]$ and $\omega_{H(e_i,e_j)} = .$ But this intervals lie on the 1st row-1st column and 2nd row -1st column respectively. So we denote $\mu_{H(e_1,e_2)}(h_1)|_{(1,1)} = [0.2, 0.3]$ and $\nu_{H(e_1,e_2)}(h_2)|_{(1,1)} = [0.3 , 0.4]$ and $\omega_{H(e_i,e_j)}|_{(1,1)} = [0.3, 0.4]$ etc to make the clear concept about what are the positions of the intervals in the relational matrices.

Defintion 7 : The order of the relational matrix is (θ , λ) , where $\theta =$ number of the universal points and $\lambda =$ number of pairs of parametrers considered in the relational matrix. In example 3 both the relational matrix for P and Q are of order (5,4). If $\theta = \lambda$,then the relational matrix is called a square matrix

Defintion 8. Let $P , Q \in \sigma_U(A \times B)$, $P = (H, A \times B)$, $Q = (J, A \times B)$ and the order of their relational matrices are same.Then we define

- (i) $P \cup Q = (H \blacksquare J, A \times B)$ where $H \blacksquare J : A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as $(H \blacksquare J)(e_i, e_j) = H(e_i, e_j) \vee J(e_j, e_j)$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$, where $\vee$ denotes the interval valued neutrosophic union.
- (ii) $P \cap Q = (H \diamond J, A \times B)$ where $H \diamond J : A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as $(H \diamond J)(e_i, e_j) = H(e_i, e_j) \wedge J(e_i, e_j)$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$, where $\wedge$ denotes the interval valued neutrosophic intersection
- (iii) $P^c = (\sim H, A \times B)$, where $\sim H : A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as $\sim H(e_i, e_j) = [H(e_i, e_j)]^c$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$, where c denotes the interval valued neutrosophic complement.

Example 4 .Consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F,A) and (G,B) given in example 3. Let us consider the two IVNSS-relations P_1 and Q_1 given below:

$P_1 = (J, A \times B)$:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.3,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.3, 0.6],[0.2, 1]]
h ₂	[[0.1,0.3],[0.4, 0.5],[1, 1]]	[[0.1, 0.2],[0, 0],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.4],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.3],[0.3,0.6]]	[[0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.4]]
h ₄	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 1]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.4,0.5]]	[[0, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5],[0.6,0.7]]

$Q_1=(J, A \times B)$:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.5, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.5],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[1, 1]]
h ₂	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[1, 1]]	[[0.4, 0.6],[0.2, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.4, 0.5],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.2],[1, 1]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.5, 0.6],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[1, 1]]	[[0.7, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0,0.4]]
h ₄	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0, 1]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.6,0.7]]

Then $P_1 \cup Q_1$:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.5, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.3 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0.2, 1]]
h ₂	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[1, 1]]	[[0.4, 0.6],[0.2, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.4],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1]]	[[0.7, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0,0.4]]
h ₄	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0, 1]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.6,0.7]]

$P_1 \cap Q_1$:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.5]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.6],[1, 1]]
h ₂	[[0.1, 0.3],[0.4, 0.5],[1, 1]]	[[0.1, 0.2],[0.2, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.4, 0.5],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[1, 1]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.5, 0.6],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[1, 1]]	[[0.7, 0.8],[0.1, 0.3],[0.3,0.6]]	[[0.2, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0,0.4]]
h ₄	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 1]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.4,0.5]]	[[0, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5],[0.6,0.7]]

P_1^c

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.1, 0.2],[0.6, 0.7],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.5, 0.7],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.3 0.5],[0.6, 0.7],[0.3,0.5]]	[[0.2, 1],[0.4, 0.7],[0.4, 0.5]]
h ₂	[[1, 1],[0.5, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[1, 1],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.4,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.6, 0.8],[0.3, 0.5]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.6, 0.9],[0.2,0.6]]	[[1, 1],[0.7, 0.9],[0.2, 0.6]]	[[0.3, 0.6],[0.7, 0.9],[0.2,0.3]]	[[0, 0.4],[0.7, 0.8],[0.2,0.5]]
h ₄	[[0, 0.1],[0.5, 0.7],[0.2, 0.4]]	[[0.1, 0.2],[0.5, 0.6],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.6, 0.7],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.6, 0.7],[0.5, 0.6],[0,0.2]]

Theorem 1. Let $P, Q, R \in \sigma_U(Ax B)$ and the order of their relational matrices are same. Then the following properties hold:

- a) $(P \cup Q)^c = P^c \cap Q^c$
- b) $(P \cap Q)^c = P^c \cup Q^c$
- c) $P \cup (Q \cap R) = (P \cup Q) \cap R$
- d) $P \cap (Q \cup R) = (P \cap Q) \cup R$
- e) $P \cap (Q \cup R) = (P \cap Q) \cup (P \cap R)$
- f) $P \cup (Q \cap R) = (P \cup Q) \cap (P \cup R)$

Proof. a) let $P = (H, Ax B), Q = (J, Ax B)$. then $P \cup Q = (H \blacksquare J, Ax B)$, where $H \blacksquare J: Ax B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as

$$(H \blacksquare J)(e_i, e_j) = H(e_i, e_j) \vee J(e_i, e_j) \text{ for } (e_i, e_j) \in A \times B.$$

So $(P \cup Q)^c = (\sim H \blacksquare J, Ax B)$, where $\sim H \blacksquare J: A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as $(\sim H \blacksquare J)(e_i, e_j)$

$$= [H(e_i, e_j) \vee J(e_i, e_j)]^c$$

$$= \{ \langle h_k, \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) \rangle : h_k \in U \} \vee \{ \langle$$

$$h_k, \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) \rangle : h_k \in U \}^c$$

$$= \{ \langle h_k, [\max(\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \max(\sup \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)),$$

$$[\min(\inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \min(\sup \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)],$$

$$[\min(\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \min(\sup \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)] \rangle : h_k \in U \}^c$$

$$= \{ \langle h_k, [\min(\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \min(\sup \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)),$$

$$[1 - \min(\sup \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), 1 - \min(\inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)],$$

$$[\max(\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \max(\sup \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)] \rangle : h_k \in U \}$$

Now $P^c \cap Q^c = (\sim H, A \times B) \cap (\sim J, A \times B)$, where $\sim H, \sim J: A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ are defined as

$$\sim H(e_i, e_j) = [H(e_i, e_j)]^c \text{ and } \sim J(e_i, e_j) = [J(e_i, e_j)]^c \text{ for } (e_i, e_j) \in A \times B, \text{ we have}$$

$$(\sim H, A \times B) \cap (\sim J, A \times B) = (\sim H \diamond \sim J, A \times B)(e_i, e_j)$$

Now for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$, $(\sim H \diamond \sim J)(e_i, e_j) = \sim H(e_j, e_j) \wedge \sim J(e_i, e_j) =$

$$\{ \langle h_k, [\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)], [1 - \sup \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), 1 - \inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)], [\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \sup \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)] \rangle : h_k \in U \}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \wedge \{ \langle h_k, [\inf \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \text{Sup} \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)], [1 - \text{Sup} \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), 1 - \inf \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)], [\inf \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \text{Sup} \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)] \rangle : h_k \in U \} \\ & = \{ \langle h_k, [\min (\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \min (\text{Sup} \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \text{Sup} \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)),], \\ & [\max ((1 - \text{Sup} \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), (1 - \text{Sup} \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k))), \max ((1 - \inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), (1 - \inf \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)))] \}, \\ & [\max (\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \max (\text{Sup} \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \text{Sup} \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k))] \rangle : h_k \in U \} \\ & = \{ \langle h_k, [\min (\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \min (\text{sup} \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \text{sup} \omega_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)),], \\ & [1 - \min (\text{sup} \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \text{sup} \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), 1 - \min (\inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \nu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k))], \\ & [\max (\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \inf \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)), \max (\text{sup} \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \text{sup} \mu_{J(e_i, e_j)}(h_k))] \rangle : h_k \in U \} \end{aligned}$$

Then, $(P \cup Q)^c = P^c \cap Q^c$

b) Proof is similar to a)

c) let $P = (H, A \times B)$, $Q = (J, A \times B)$ and $R = (K, A \times B)$. Then $P \cup Q = (H \blacksquare J, A \times B)$, where $H \blacksquare J : A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as $(H \blacksquare J)(e_i, e_j) = H(e_i, e_j) \vee J(e_i, e_j)$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$.

So $(P \cup Q) \cup R = ((H \blacksquare J) \blacksquare K, A \times B)$, where $(H \blacksquare J) \blacksquare K : A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ $(H \blacksquare J) \blacksquare K(e_i, e_j) = H(e_i, e_j) \vee J(e_i, e_j) \vee K(e_i, e_j)$. Now as

$(H(e_i, e_j) \vee J(e_i, e_j)) \vee K(e_i, e_j) = H(e_i, e_j) \vee (J(e_i, e_j) \vee K(e_i, e_j))$. therefore

$(H \blacksquare J) \blacksquare K(e_i, e_j) = ((H \blacksquare (J \blacksquare K))(e_i, e_j)$, Also we have $P \cup (Q \cup R) = (P \cup Q) \cup R = (H \blacksquare (J \blacksquare K), A \times B)$. consequently, $P \cup (Q \cup R) = (P \cup Q) \cup R$

d) Proof is similar to c)

e) let $P = (H, A \times B)$, $Q = (J, A \times B)$ and $R = (K, A \times B)$. Then $Q \cup R = (J \blacksquare K, A \times B)$, where $J \blacksquare K : A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as $(J \blacksquare K)(e_i, e_j) = J(e_i, e_j) \vee K(e_i, e_j)$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$.

Then $P \cap (Q \cup R) = (H \diamond (J \blacksquare K), A \times B)$, where $H \diamond (J \blacksquare K) : A \times B \rightarrow IVNS(U)$ is defined as for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$, $(H \diamond (J \blacksquare K))(e_i, e_j) = H(e_i, e_j) \wedge (J(e_i, e_j) \vee K(e_i, e_j))$.

since $H(e_i, e_j) \wedge (J(e_i, e_j) \vee K(e_i, e_j)) = (H(e_i, e_j) \wedge (J(e_i, e_j))) \vee (H(e_i, e_j) \wedge K(e_i, e_j))$. We have $(H \diamond (J \blacksquare K))(e_i, e_j) = (H(e_i, e_j) \wedge (J(e_i, e_j))) \vee (H(e_i, e_j) \wedge K(e_i, e_j))$.

Also we have $(P \cap Q) \cup (P \cap R) = (H \diamond J, A \times B) \cup (H \diamond K, A \times B) = ((H \diamond J) \blacksquare (H \diamond K), A \times B)$ Now for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$, $((H \diamond J) \blacksquare (H \diamond K))(e_i, e_j) = (H \diamond J)(e_i, e_j) \vee (H \diamond K)(e_i, e_j) = (H(e_i, e_j) \wedge J(e_i, e_j)) \vee (H(e_i, e_j) \wedge K(e_i, e_j)) = (H \diamond (J \blacksquare K))(e_i, e_j)$. consequently, $P \cap (Q \cup R) = (P \cap Q) \cup (P \cap R)$.

f) Proof is similar to e)

Definition 9. Let $P, Q \in \sigma_U(A \times B)$ and the order of their relational matrices are same. Then $P \subseteq Q$ if $H(e_i, e_j) \subseteq J(e_i, e_j)$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ where $P = (H, A \times B)$ and $Q = (J, A \times B)$

Example 5:

P

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h_1	$([0.2, 0.3], [0.2, 0.3], [0.4, 0.5])$	$([0.2, 0.3], [0.7, 0.8], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.7, 0.8], [0.2, 0.5])$	$([0.4, 0.6], [0.7, 0.8], [0.5, 0.6])$
h_2	$([0.4, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.8])$	$([1, 1], [0, 0], [0, 0])$	$([0.1, 0.5], [0.4, 0.7], [0.5, 0.6])$	$([0.1, 0.3], [0.4, 0.7], [0.5, 0.6])$
h_3	$([0.2, 0.4], [0.3, 0.4], [0.3, 0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.5], [0.4, 0.6], [0.2, 0.5])$	$([1, 1], [0, 0], [0, 0])$	$([0.1, 0.2], [0.4, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5])$
h_4	$([0.3, 0.5], [0.3, 0.4], [0.3, 0.6])$	$([0.2, 0.3], [0.7, 0.9], [0.4, 0.5])$	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.7, 0.9], [0.3, 0.4])$	$([0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.5], [0.5, 0.6])$

Q

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h_1	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.1, 0.4])$	$([0.5, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.1, 0.4])$	$([0.5, 0.7], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4])$
h_2	$([0.6, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4], [0.1, 0.7])$	$([1, 1], [0, 0], [0, 0])$	$([0.3, 0.6], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.3])$	$([0.3, 0.5], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.4])$
h_3	$([0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2])$	$([0.4, 0.7], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([1, 1], [0, 0], [0, 0])$	$([0.4, 0.7], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.4])$
h_4	$([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.4, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2])$	$([0.4, 0.6], [0.1, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2])$	$([0.4, 0.5], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3])$

Definition 10 : Let U be an initial universe and (F, A) and (G, B) be two interval valued neutrosophic soft sets. Then a null relation between them is denoted

by O_U and is defined as $O_U = (H_0, A \times B)$ where $H_0(e_i, e_j) = \{ \langle h_k, [0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1] \rangle; h_k \in U \}$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$.

Example 6. Consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) given in example 3. Then a null relation between them is given by

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h_1	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$
h_2	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$
h_3	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$
h_4	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$	$([0, 0], [1, 1], [1, 1])$

Remark 2 . It can be easily seen that $P \cup O_U = P$ and $P \cap O_U = O_U$ for any $P \in \sigma_U(A \times B)$

Definition 11 : Let U be an initial universe and (F, A) and (G, B) be two interval valued neutrosophic soft sets. Then an absolute relation between them is denoted

by I_U and is defined as $I_U = (H_1, A \times B)$ where $H_1(e_i, e_j) = \{ \langle h_k, [1, 1], [0, 0], [0, 0] \rangle; h_k \in U \}$ for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$.

Example 7. Consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) given in example 3. Then an absolute relation between them is given by

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h ₁	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])
h ₂	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])
h ₃	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])
h ₄	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])

Remark 3 . It can be easily seen that $P \cup I_U = I_U$ and $P \cap I_U = P$ for any $P \in \sigma_U(Ax B)$

Definition 12 :Let τ be a sub-collection of interval valued neutrosophic soft set relations of the same order belonging to $\sigma_U(Ax B)$.Then τ is said to form a relational topology over $\sigma_U(Ax B)$ if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) $O_U, I_U \in \tau$
- (ii) If
- (iii) If $P_1, P_2 \in \tau$, then $P_1 \cap P_2 \in \tau$

Then we say that $(\sigma_U(Ax B) , \tau)$ is a conditional relational topological space

Example 8: Consider example 3. Then the collection $\tau=\{O_U, I_U, P, Q\}$ forms a relational topology on $\sigma_U(Ax B)$.

IV .Various type of interval valued neutrosophic soft relation

In this section , we present some basic properties of IVNSS relation. Let $P \in \sigma_U(Ax B)$ and $P=(H, A xB)$ and $Q=(J, A xB)$ whose relational matrix is a square matrix

Defintion 13. An IVNSS-relation P is said to be reflexive if for $(e_i, e_j) \in A x B$ and $h_k \in U$, such that $\mu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = [1, 1]$, $\nu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = [0, 0]$ and $\omega_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = [0 0]$ for $m = n=k$

Example 9: $U =\{h_1 , h_2 , h_3, h_4\}$ Let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) where $A= \{e_1, e_3 \}$ and $B =\{e_2, e_4 \}$ then a reflexive IVNSS-relation between them is

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h ₁	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([0.4, 0.6],[0.7, 0.8],[0.1,0.4])	([0.4, 0.6],[0.7, 0.8],[0.1,0.4])	([0.4, 0.6],[0.7, 0.8],[0.1,0.4])
h ₂	([0.6, 0.8],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.7])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([0.1, 0.5],[0.4, 0.7],[0.5,0.6])	([0.1, 0.5],[0.4, 0.7],[0.5,0.6])
h ₃	([0.3, 0.6],[0.2, 0.7],[0.3,0.4])	([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])
h ₄	([0.6, 0.7],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.4])	([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])	([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])

Defintion 14. An IVNSS-relation P is said to be anti- reflexive if for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ and $h_k \in U$, such that $\mu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = [0, 0]$, $\nu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = [0, 0]$ and $\omega_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = [1 1]$ for $m = n=k$

Example 10: let $U =\{h_1 , h_2 , h_3, h_4\}$. Let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) where $A= \{e_1, e_3 \}$ an $B =\{e_2, e_4\}$ then an anti-reflexive IVNSS-relation between them is

U	(e_1 ,e_2)	(e_1 ,e_4)	(e_3 ,e_2)	(e_3 ,e_4)
h_1	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.7, 0.8],[0.1,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.7, 0.8],[0.1,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.7, 0.8],[0.1,0.4])$
h_2	$([0.6, 0.8],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.7])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$	$([0.1, 0.5],[0.4, 0.7],[0.5,0.6])$	$([0.1, 0.5],[0.4, 0.7],[0.5,0.6])$
h_3	$([0.3, 0.6],[0.2, 0.7],[0.3,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$	$([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])$
h_4	$([0.6, 0.7],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$

Defintion 15. An IVNSS-relation P is said to be symmetric if for $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ and $h_k \in U$, $\exists (e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ and $h_1 \in U$ such that $\mu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = \mu_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)}$, $\nu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = \nu_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)}$ and $\omega_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = \omega_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)}$

Example 11: let $U =\{h_1 , h_2 , h_3, h_4\}$. Let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) where $A= \{e_1, e_3 \}$ an $B =\{e_2, e_4\}$ then a symmetric IVNSS-relation between them is

U	(e_1 ,e_2)	(e_1 ,e_4)	(e_3 ,e_2)	(e_3 ,e_4)
h_1	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0.5, 0.6],[0.6, 0.7],[0.3,0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.6],[0.5, 0.7],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.3 0.4],[0.3,0.4])$
h_2	$([0.5, 0.6],[0.6, 0.7],[0.3,0.4])$	$([0, 0],[1, 1],[1, 1])$	$([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$
h_3	$([0.3, 0.6],[0.5, 0.7],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])$	$([0.4, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.4])$
h_4	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.3 0.4],[0.3,0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0.4, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.4])$	$([0.2, 0.7],[0.3, 0.4],[0.6,0.7])$

Defintion 16. An IVNSS-relation P is said to be anti-symmetric if for each $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ and $h_k \in U$, $\exists (e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ and $h_1 \in U$ such that either $\mu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} \neq \mu_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)}$, $\nu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} \neq \nu_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)}$ and $\omega_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} \neq \omega_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)}$ or $\mu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = \mu_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)}$ [0, 0] , $\nu_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = \nu_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)} = [0 ,0]$ and $\omega_{H(e_i,e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} = \omega_{H(e_p,e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)} = [1 , 1]$

Example 12: let $U =\{h_1 , h_2 , h_3, h_4\}$. Let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) where $A= \{e_1, e_3 \}$ an $B =\{e_2, e_4\}$ then an anti-symmetric IVNSS-relation between them is

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h_1	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0.5, 0.6],[0.6, 0.7],[0.3,0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.6],[0.5, 0.7],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$
h_2	$([0.5, 0.6],[0.6, 0.7],[0.3,0.4])$	$([0, 0],[1, 1],[1, 1])$	$([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$
h_3	$([0.3, 0.6],[0.5, 0.7],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])$	$([0.4, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.4])$
h_4	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$	$([0.2, 0.7],[0.3, 0.4],[0.6,0.7])$

Definition 17 . An IVNSS-relation P is said to be perfectly anti-symmetric if for each $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ and $h_k \in U$, $\exists (e_i, e_j) \in A \times B$ and $h_1 \in U$ such that whenever $\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} > 0$, $\inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} > 0$ and $\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k)|_{(m,n)} > 0$, $\mu_{H(e_p, e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)} = [0, 0]$, $\nu_{H(e_p, e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)} = [0, 0]$ and $\omega_{H(e_p, e_q)}(h_1)|_{(n,m)} = [1, 1]$

Example 13: let $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4\}$. Let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) where $A = \{e_1, e_3\}$ and $B = \{e_2, e_4\}$ then a perfectly anti-symmetric IVNSS-relation between them is

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
h_1	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0.5, 0.6],[0.6, 0.7],[0.3,0.4])$	$([0.3, 0.6],[0.5, 0.7],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$
h_2	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$	$([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$
h_3	$([0.3, 0.6],[0.5, 0.7],[0.2,0.4])$	$([0, 0],[0, 0],[1, 1])$	$([0.4, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])$	$([0, 0.5],[0, 0.4],[0,0.4])$
h_4	$([0, 0.6],[0, 0.2],[0, 1])$	$([0.3, 0.4],[0.7, 0.9],[0.1,0.2])$	$([0, 0.6],[0, 0.3],[0,0.5])$	$([0.2, 0.7],[0.3, 0.4],[0.6,0.7])$

In the following, we define two composite of interval valued neutrosophic soft relation.

Definition 18 : Let $P, Q \in \sigma_U(A \times A)$ and $P = (H, A \times A)$, $Q = (J, A \times A)$ and the order of their relational matrices are same. Then the composition of P and Q, denoted by $P * Q$ is defined by $P * Q = (H \circ J, A \times A)$ where $H \circ J : A \times A \rightarrow IVNS(U)$

Is defined as $(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j) = \{ \langle h_k, \mu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \nu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \omega_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) \rangle : h_k \in U \}$

Where

$$\mu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) = [\max_l(\min(\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \mu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k))), \max_l(\min(\sup \mu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \mu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)))]$$

$$\nu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) = [\min_l(\max(\inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \nu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k))), \min_l(\max(\sup \nu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \nu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)))]$$

And

$$\omega_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) = [\min_l(\max(\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \omega_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k))), \min_l(\max(\sup \omega_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \omega_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)))]$$

For $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times A$

Example 14: $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4\}$.let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F,A) and (G,A) where $A = \{e_1, e_2\}$.Let $P, Q \in \sigma_U(A \times A)$ and $P = (H, A \times A)$, $Q = (J, A \times A)$ where P:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[0.2, 0.3]]
h ₂	[[1, 1],[0, 0],[1, 1]]	[[0.1, 0.2],[0, 0],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.3,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.4],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.4]]
h ₄	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 1]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5]]	[[0, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5],[0.6,0.7]]

Q:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.5, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.5],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[1, 1]]
h ₂	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[1, 1]]	[[0.4, 0.6],[0.2, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.4, 0.5],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.2],[1, 1]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.5, 0.6],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[1, 1]]	[[0.7, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0,0.4]]
h ₄	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0, 1]]	[[0.3, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.6,0.7]]

Then

P*Q

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2]]	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.2,0.3]]	[[0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.3],[0.2, 0.6],[0.3, 0.4]]
h ₂	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5]]	[[0.1, 0.6],[0.1, 0.2],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.3, 0.5]]
h ₃	[[0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[0,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1, 0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0.2,0.4]]	[[0.2, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.5]]
h ₄	[[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 0.2]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.2, 0.5],[0.3,0.4]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.2, 0.4],[0.2,0.5]]	[[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.5]]

Definition 19 : Let $P, Q \in \sigma_U(A \times A)$ and $P = (H, A \times A)$, $Q = (J, A \times A)$ and the order of their relational matrices are same. Then the composition of P and Q, denoted by $P \circ Q$ is defined by $P \circ Q = (H \circ J, A \times A)$ where $H \circ J : A \times A \rightarrow IVNS(U)$

Is defined as $(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j) = \{ \langle h_k, \mu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \nu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k), \omega_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) \rangle : h_k \in U \}$

Where

$$\mu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) = [\min_l(\max(\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \mu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k))), \min_l(\max(\sup \mu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \mu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)))]$$

$$\nu_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) = [\max_l(\min(\inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \nu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k))), \max_l(\min(\sup \nu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \nu_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)))]$$

And

$$\omega_{(H \circ J)(e_i, e_j)}(h_k) = [\max_l(\min(\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \omega_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k))), \max_l(\min(\sup \omega_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \omega_{J(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)))]$$

For $(e_i, e_j) \in A \times A$

Example 15 : Let $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4\}$. let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F,A) and (G,A) where $A = \{e_1, e_2\}$. Let $P, Q \in \sigma_U(A \times A)$ and $P = (H, A \times A)$, $Q = (J, A \times A)$ where P:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[(0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2)]	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.4)]	[(0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.3,0.4)]	[(0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[0.2, 0.3)]
h ₂	[[1, 1],[0, 0],[1, 1)]	[(0.1, 0.2],[0, 0],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.3,0.5)]	[(0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1)]
h ₃	[(0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.4],[0.3,0.4)]	[(0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1)]	[(0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.4)]
h ₄	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 1)]	[(0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5)]	[(0, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5],[0.6,0.7)]

Q:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[(0.5, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.1,0.2)]	[(0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[0.3,0.4)]	[(0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.5],[0.2,0.4)]	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[1, 1)]
h ₂	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[1, 1)]	[(0.4, 0.6],[0.2, 0.3],[0.2,0.4)]	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.4, 0.5],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.2],[1, 1)]
h ₃	[(0.2, 0.3],[0.5, 0.6],[0.2,0.4)]	[(0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[1, 1)]	[(0.7, 0.8],[0.1, 0.2],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0,0.4)]
h ₄	[(0.3, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0, 1)]	[(0.3, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.1,0.2)]	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5)]	[(0.3, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[0.6,0.7)]

Then

P◦Q

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	[(0.2, 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.3,0.4)]	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.3,0.4)]	[(0.2 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.4)]	[(0.2, 0.3],[0.2, 0.6],[0.3, 0.4)]
h ₂	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2, 0.5)]	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.3,0.5)]	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1)]
h ₃	[(0.2, 0.3],[0.2, 0.3],[1,1)]	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5)]	[(0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.2, 0.5],[0.1 0.3],[1,1)]
h ₄	[(0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.7)]	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.2, 0.5],[0.4, 0.5],[0.2,0.5)]	[(0.2, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0.6,0.7)]

Definition 20 : Let $P \in \sigma_U(Ax A)$ and $P=(H, Ax A)$. Then P is called transitive IVNSS-relation if $P * P \subseteq P$, i.e $\cup(H(e_i, e_l) \cap H(e_l, e_j)) \subseteq H(e_i, e_j)$, i.e,

$$\text{Max}(\inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \mu_{H(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)) \leq \inf \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k),$$

$$\text{Max}(\sup \mu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \mu_{H(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)) \leq \sup \mu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k),$$

$$\text{Min}(\inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \nu_{H(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)) \leq \inf \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k),$$

$$\text{Min}(\sup \nu_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \nu_{H(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)) \leq \sup \nu_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k),$$

$$\text{Min}(\inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \inf \omega_{H(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)) \leq \inf \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k),$$

$$\text{Min}(\sup \omega_{H(e_i, e_l)}(h_k), \sup \omega_{H(e_l, e_j)}(h_k)) \leq \sup \omega_{H(e_i, e_j)}(h_k),$$

Example 16: Let $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4\}$.let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F,A) and (G,A) where $A = \{e_1, e_2\}$. Let $P, Q \in \sigma_U(Ax A)$ and $P=(H, Ax A)$, $Q=(J, Ax A)$ where P:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	([0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2])	([0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.4])	([0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.4])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[1, 1])
h ₂	([1, 1],[0, 0],[1, 1])	([0.1, 0.2],[0, 0],[0.2,0.4])	([0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])	([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1])
h ₃	([0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.4],[0.2,0.4])	([0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])	([0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.4])
h ₄	([0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 1])	([0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[0.1,0.2])	([0.3, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5])	([0, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5],[0.6,0.7])

Then P*P

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)	(e_3, e_4)
H1	([0.3, 0.4],[0.3, 0.4],[0.1,0.2])	([0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0.3,0.4])	([0.2 0.5],[0.3, 0.4],[0.2,0.4])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.3, 0.6],[1, 1])
h ₂	([1, 1],[0, 0],[1, 1])	([0.1, 0.2],[0, 0],[0.2,0.4])	([0.4, 0.5],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])	([0.4, 0.7],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1])
h ₃	([0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.4],[0.2,0.4])	([0.2, 0.6],[0.1, 0.3],[1, 1])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.3],[0.2,0.5])	([0.2, 0.5],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.4])
h ₄	([0.2, 0.4],[0.3, 0.5],[0, 1])	([0.3, 0.4],[0.4, 0.5],[0.1,0.2])	([0.3, 0.4],[0.2, 0.3],[0,0.5])	([0, 0.2],[0.4, 0.5],[0.6,0.7])

Thus, $P * P \subseteq P$ and so P is a transitive IVNSS-relation.

Definition 21 . Let $P \in \sigma_U(Ax A)$ and $P = (H, Ax A)$. Then P is called equivalence IVNSS-relation if P satisfies the following conditions:

- 1) Reflexivity (see definition 13).
- 2) Symmetry (see definition 15).
- 3) Transitivity (see definition 20).

Example 17: Let $U = \{h_1, h_2, h_3\}$. let us consider the interval valued neutrosophic soft sets (F, A) where $A = \{e_1, e_2\}$. Let $P, Q \in \sigma_U(Ax A)$ and $P = (H, Ax A)$, where P:

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)
h ₁	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.2, 0.4],[0.3,0.4])	([0.1, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.2,0.3])
h ₂	([0.2, 0.3],[0.4, 0.6],[0.3,0.4])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.5],[0.2,0.3])
h ₃	([0.1, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.2,0.3])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.5],[0.2,0.3])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])

P*P

U	(e_1, e_2)	(e_1, e_4)	(e_3, e_2)
h ₁	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.2, 0.4],[0.3,0.4])	([0.1, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.2,0.3])
h ₂	([0.2, 0.3],[0.4, 0.6],[0.3,0.4])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.5],[0.2,0.3])
h ₃	([0.1, 0.5],[0.2, 0.4],[0.2,0.3])	([0.2, 0.3],[0.1, 0.5],[0.2,0.3])	([1, 1],[0, 0],[0, 0])

Then P is equivalence IVNSS-relation

Conclusions

In this paper we have defined, for the first time, the notion of interval neutrosophic soft relation. We have studied some properties for interval neutrosophic soft relation. We hope that this paper will promote the future study on IVNSS and IVNSS relation to carry out a general framework for their application in practical life.

Acknowledgements

The authors are very grateful to the anonymous referees for their insightful and constructive comments and suggestions, which have been very helpful in improving the paper.

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